

THE EFFECT OF POST-WELDING COOLING RATE ON THE STRENGTH OF TCW JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Thermoset composite welding (TCW) is a patented technology that allows two carbon-epoxy components, manufactured with specific thermoplastic surfaces to be welded together. Heat and pressure are applied in a controlled environment to ensure uniform welding stress across the joint. The thermoplastic weld material has a significantly higher coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) than the carbon-epoxy composite laminate, especially in the laminate in-plane direction. This causes thermal residual stresses to build up during the cooling stage of the welding process.

In such a situation, one of the many factors that can affect the magnitude of thermal residual stress is the cooling rate experienced by the joint after welding. This study focuses on the effect of the cooling rate on the strength of the joint. Single lap shear joints were welded using two different cooling rates, and then subsequently loaded to failure.

The results showed that specimens with a lower cooling rate have an equal or higher joint strength than those with a higher cooling rate. This indicates that some aspect of the joint, affected by the cooling rate, may have a significant effect on the ultimate shear strength of the joint. Inspection of the fracture surfaces suggests more plastic deformation of the thermoplastic weld polymer in the fracture surfaces of the specimens with the lower cooling rate.

1 INTRODUCTION

The presence of thermal residual stress in most composites is a well-known effect due to the differences between the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the matrix and the fibre. When composites are joined together by use of adhesives, the CTE differences between the laminates and the adhesive can pose another significant build-up of thermal residual stresses in the vicinity of the joint. Thermal residual stresses start to form when the component is cooled down from the fabrication temperature to its operating temperature due to the differential thermal contraction experienced by the adherend and the adhesive. The residual stresses become more apparent when the operating temperature is considerably lower than the fabrication temperature.

Thermoset Composite Welding (TCW) technology is a patented technology developed by CRC-ACS in which a thermoset composite prepreg layup is surfaced with an integrated layer of thermoplastic. Cured laminates with this integrated thermoplastic layer can then be welded together to form a welded assembly. The thermoplastic layer used is an unreinforced semi-crystalline polymer and naturally has a higher in-plane CTE than the carbon-epoxy laminate.

Especially where the operating temperature of joints is low (the nominal minimum operating temperature of aircraft structure is commonly quoted as -55°C) thermal residual stresses in the joints may be important. Therefore, it is important to understand the factors influencing the magnitude of the thermal residual stresses formed in TCW joints and their effect on the joint strength.

One of the inherent problems with thermal residual stresses in composite laminates is the difficulty to measure these directly or to quantify them. As composite laminates, by definition, use materials with different CTEs, it will not be possible to completely eliminate the residual stresses from being formed. There are plenty of methods proposed by many researchers to characterise such stresses [1], including the bi-material strip method [2]. However, these methods are less useful for measuring the thermal residual stresses in a joint such as a TCW joint. This is due to TCW joint having at least two sources of thermal residual stresses: the first is from the in-plane CTE mismatch between the composite adherend and thermoplastic weld polymer; the second source is from the CTE mismatch between the fibre and matrix within the composite laminate itself. Due to this complexity, it is very difficult to isolate the contribution of the thermal residual stresses from one source or the other. This paper will instead focus on attempts to alter the magnitude of the thermal residual stresses, by controlling the manufacturing parameters, as an indirect way of measuring the effect of thermal residual stresses on the TCW joint strength.

Studies have found that the performance of a thermoplastic can be affected by several factors including the cooling rate used during fabrication process [3, 4]. The rate of cooling of a thermoplastic can affect its degree of crystallisation and crystallite size, which will then affect its mechanical properties [4-6]. In work done by Choo, a finite element model is created to predict the residual stress in a continuous fibre reinforced composite with varying cooling rates [7]. The results show that the slower cooling rate allows more time for the residual stress to relax, thus lowering the axial stress in the model [7]. Another study, conducted by Gao on a carbon fibre / semi-crystalline polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite, shows that increasing the cooling rate leads to a decrease in the degree of crystallinity and in the spherulite size of the PEEK [4]. These effects from the increase in cooling rate led to a decrease in tensile strength and elastic modulus of PEEK [4]. These results from Choo and Gao provide an insight into the effect of cooling rate on semi-crystalline thermoplastic where there are two competing mechanisms that can affect the mechanical behaviour of the TCW joint [4, 7]: namely the different stress relaxation due to the different amount of time a joint has spent in the high temperature range; and the difference in mechanical properties of the thermoplastic due to the different processing parameters (in this case the rate of cooling from the welding temperature). In this study, the focus will be placed on the latter effect, while leaving the stress relaxation effect for another study. However, the authors believe that both factors can significantly influence the joint performance and shall be considered together in future work.

The thermoplastic weld polymer used in this investigation of TCW joints is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic with a glass transition temperature between -55°C and room temperature. Therefore the weld polymer will be below its glass transition temperature for part of this operating temperature range.

In the formation of a TCW joint, the thermoplastic weld polymer will be subjected to different conditions, including high temperatures, high pressures, varying cooling rate from welding temperature and finally different operating temperatures. All these parameters can have an effect on the formation of thermal residual stresses and subsequently on the performance of the TCW joint. This paper will focus on the effect of cooling rate after welding and component operating temperature on the TCW joint strength.

2 SPECIMEN PREPARATION

A TCW joint is manufactured by welding two thermoplastic-surfaced composite laminates. The laminates used in this work were made from Hexcel M21 T700GC prepreg. The laminates were laid up with a configuration of $[0/90]_{5S}$. A single layer of weld polymer 0.125 mm thick was included on one surface of the lay-up. The laminate was cured in an autoclave following the prepreg manufacturer's standard cure cycle.

For the welding process, the weld polymer surfaces were first cleaned using isopropyl alcohol. The joints were then assembled, vacuum bagged, and placed in an oven for welding. The joint was then cooled down, at different cooling rates, before removal of the vacuum bag. The cooling process was controlled manually to ensure a cooling rate as consistent as possible. The average cooling rate is presented in Table 1 below.

Cooling Rate	[°C/min]
Fast	4.420
Slow	0.362

Table 1: Average cooling rate of the TCW joints

The single-lap joint specimens were made by slitting the welded panel using diamond-tipped saw blades (with water cooling) to the final dimensions shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dimensions of the single-lap shear specimen

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

In order to study the effect of cooling rate at different test temperatures, the specimens were tested to failure at three temperatures, -55°C , room temperature, and 90°C . An environment chamber was used for the low and high temperature tests. Liquid nitrogen was used to create the -55°C temperature environment. Specimens in the low- and high-temperature environments were fitted with a thermocouple and were tested at least three minutes after reaching the desired temperature.

The single lap joint was loaded in tension on an INSTRON machine, at a loading rate of 3mm/min, to failure. The maximum load recorded was used to calculate the average shear stress of the single lap joint with the following formula.

$$\tau = \frac{F}{A} \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, the fracture surface was observed under both an optical microscope and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to observe any differences in joint micro structure or failure mode.

The setup of the experiment in an environmental chamber can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Setup of the single-lap shear specimen in environmental chamber

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Effects of Operating Temperature

The average lap shear strengths obtained from the specimens are presented in Table 2 below.

The highest shear strength was measured at room temperature. At elevated and low temperature, the average shear strength was lower. Fracture surfaces indicate that the failure was dominantly ductile at high temperature and room temperature and more brittle at the low temperature.

Temperature (°C)	Average Max Stress (MPa)	
	Fast Cooling Rate	Slow Cooling Rate
-55	24.05	23.66
23	33.90	39.56
90	18.52	22.10

Table 2: Effect of test temperature on the joint average shear strength

4.2 Effect of Cooling Rate

At room temperature and higher, the slower cooling rate produced joints with higher shear strength. However at low temperature this did not apply. With the slower cooling rate, the lap shear strength is 2% lower at -55°C, but 17% higher at room temperature and 19% higher at 90°C.

The data from Table 2 is reorganised to highlight the effect of cooling rate as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Effect of cooling rate on the average shear strength

4.3 Failure Surfaces

The specimens tested at room temperature and 90°C show clear signs of plastic deformation before failure, especially for the specimens tested at high temperature. Significant whitening of the weld polymer can be observed at each end of the joint overlap for both room temperature and high temperature specimens, as shown in Figure 4(b) and Figure 4(c) respectively. This whitening will be further described below. The single-lap joints tested at -55°C do not exhibit any obvious plastic deformation on the fracture surface, with no obvious whitening of the surface of the weld layer, as shown in Figure 4(a).

Figure 4: Fracture surfaces of SLS specimens tested at: (a) -55°C (b) Room Temperature (c) 90°C

There were no dramatic differences in the fracture surfaces of specimens with different cooling rates following welding. After tests at room temperature and 90°C, specimens with a slower cooling rate show more whitening in the fracture surface at each end of the overlap than specimens with faster cooling rate. These differences can be seen in Figure 5 below, which shows the failure surface of a fast cooling rate specimen and a slow cooling rate specimen tested at room temperature. The whitened area in the slowly-cooled specimen is approximately 38% larger than in the fast-cooled specimen.

A closer inspection was made of the region circled in Figure 5(b), using the SEM. This indicated that the whitening effect is due to ridges of weld polymer being formed during failure as shown in Figure 6.

(a) (b)
Figure 5: Fracture surfaces of specimens tested at room temperature:
(a) Fast Cooling Rate (b) Slow Cooling Rate

Figure 6: SEM image of fracture surface with “whitened” weld polymer from the circled area shown in Figure 5(b)

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Temperature Effect

As expected, the test temperature has a significant impact on TCW joint performance. At room temperature and 90°C, the joints appear to fail only after significant plastic deformation. Joint strength may thus be most influenced by the properties of the weld polymer. At -55°C, which is below the glass transition temperature of the weld polymer, there is little opportunity for plastic deformation and the stress concentrations in the joint appear to be more important.

5.2 Cooling Rate Effect

The difference in the joint strength between specimens cooled at different rates may be due to differences in microstructure (crystallinity), or in residual stresses, or both. Since the weld polymer is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic, the changes in cooling rate can change the degree of crystallinity, as well as the size of crystallites. This can in turn affect the shrinkage of the weld polymer: greater crystallinity is likely to lead to higher shrinkage. The fast-cooled specimen is expected to have lower degree of crystallinity, as well as smaller crystallites, due to the less time available for the individual crystallites to grow. This in turn is expected to result in the weld polymer having slightly lower strength and stiffness in the joints cooled more rapidly. Further work is currently underway to examine

this theory quantitatively by measuring the degree of crystallinity as well as the crystallite size in weld polymer cooled at different rates.

The higher joint strength seen at room temperature and 90°C in slower-cooled joints could be due to higher crystallinity and the larger size of crystallites, leading to higher weld strength, or to greater relaxation in the joint because of the greater cooling time.

There was no significant difference in joint strength from different cooling rates at -55°C, below the glass transition temperature of the weld polymer. It seems likely that, for the slower-cooled joints, the benefits of greater relaxation in residual stresses during cooling might be off-set by greater crystallization shrinkage and/or higher stiffness, each of which could increase residual stress.

5.3 Fracture Morphology

The joint tested at -55°C shows a fracture surface with shear hackles formed in the interface region as seen in Figure 7(a). At room temperature and 90°C, a mix of weld polymer failure and interface region failure can be seen and the fracture surfaces show extensive plastic deformation in the weld polymer as seen in Figure 6 and Figure 7(b). The fracture morphologies reinforce the idea that the plastic deformation plays a big role in reducing the stress concentration at the ends of the overlap and delaying the ultimate joint failure, thus increasing the shear strength of the joint. Aside from the difference in the degree of “whitening”, there was no difference in the fracture surfaces of specimens cooled at different rates.

Figure 7: (a) Higher magnification detail of a fracture surface of a specimen tested at -55°C
(b) Fracture in the weld polymer in a specimen tested at room temperature

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation, TCW joints exhibited higher strength at room temperature and above when cooled down more slowly from the welding temperature. The additional strength obtained is believed to come from higher crystallinity in the weld polymer used in this case and/or greater stress relaxation during the cooling process. Joints tested at -55°C did not show any significant benefit or disadvantage from the different cooling rates.

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